

A review of spatial sound in the Java 3D API Specification (v.1.2)

by

David Murphy

Monday, December 20, 1999

Abstract

The Java 3D API specification is one of the most popular API sets for multimedia development. This paper is a review of the specification's implementation of sound spatialisation techniques. The various sound nodes are examined using the Dual Mode and Auditory Framework systems. Although it has certain spatialisation capabilities, the specification is found to be lacking in any sophisticated techniques for spatial sound rendering. To compound the issue further the techniques that are used are rather limited in their implementation.

0.0 Preamble

In previous work, the author has introduced two benchmarks for measuring the integrity of spatial rendering and associated attributes in relation to high-level programming languages [1]. The two systems involved are the Physical and Perceptual Modes (from hence on referred to as the Dual Modes) and the Auditory Framework.

To recapitulate, the Dual Mode is used to ascertain whether or not the spatial rendering is motivated by Physical or Perceptual constructs. Having established the mode upon which sound spatialisation is based one would then proceed to examine the success of the implementation by breaking down the rendering process according to an Auditory Framework.

The Auditory Framework subdivides the spatial rendering of sound into a set of four primitives: Source, Medium, Environment, and Listener. Within each subsection various parameters are considered, for example:

Source

- Radiation
- Direction
- Power
- Etc.

Others have maintained that a three-stage framework is satisfactory [2]; however the author believes that to properly assess the success of the implementation one has to differentiate between the Medium and the Environment primitives. For more detail, the reader is referred to the author's original paper that introduced the Dual Mode and Auditory Framework benchmarks [1].

0.1 Introduction

Before delving straight into the Java 3D API specification a number of key concepts and technologies need to be defined in order for the reader to understand particular conventions used within the API set.

0.1.1 What is object-oriented programming?

The basic principle underlying an object-oriented language is that each component of the program can be represented as an object and subsequently reused. This has a positive effect upon the development process as code is reused more often saving on time and reducing coding redundancy. The Java programming language is an object-oriented programming language.

The basic component in an object-oriented language is called an object. An object is generally deemed to have two representations; the first is a representation of 'real' physical entities and the second is a representation of abstract data entities. In general, an object is considered to be a self-contained unit with identifiable boundaries.

An object is derived from a set of classes. A class is a form of abstract data that is used to describe a set of parameters and properties for a particular type of object.

0.1.2 What is an API?

Application Programming Interface, or API for short, is a low-level implementation of specific elements of code that, generally, ‘talk’ to underlying hardware, or, directly to other low-level elements, i.e. of the Operating System. It is best to view an API as ‘middle-ware’, or as a ‘hardware abstraction layer’ (HAL for short) sitting between the application and the hardware.

Normally, an API consists of libraries, or code, that have a specific function. For instance, Java has an API that allows a programmer to create a graphical window. The API can facilitate this without the developer ever having to write the low-level code that tells the video display card to draw the window. Similarly, Java has an API for the rendering of 3D sound, or spatial sound rendering, which is the focus of this paper.

0.1.3 Java the language

Java is a very popular programming language. Currently, it is the language of choice for multimedia development, primarily because it is object-oriented and is ubiquitous for Internet development. Java was designed in 1990 by Sun Microsystems and, because it is a bytecode representation, the language is ideal for cross-platform development.

0.1.4 Why Java 3D API?

Although the Java 3D API specification was originally intended for 3D graphics it has proved to be a suitable vehicle for the rendering of three-dimensional sound. It makes sense from a developer’s point of view to keep all of the three-dimensional functionality within the same API set.

0.1.5 Conventions used within the Java 3D API Set

Java 3D classes are comprised of Constants, Constructors, and Methods. Below are definitions for each of these terms:

- A constant is a quantity whose value does not change during the compilation and execution of the application.
- A constructor is the object-oriented equivalent of a procedural function.
- A method is an object procedure that performs some well-defined operation on data.

1.0 Spatial Sound in the Java 3D API

The implementation of spatial sound in this revision of the Java 3D specification¹ employs a hierarchy of nodes that consist of:

Sound Node

- PointSound node
- ConeSound node
- BackgroundSound node

There are also two Java classes for defining the aural attributes of an environment. These are the Soundscape Node and the AuralAttributes Object.

Figure 1 Sound Node Hierarchy

Each node is defined in a SceneGraph. The SceneGraph is a collection of nodes that constitute the three-dimensional environment. The application reads the nodes and their associated parameters from the SceneGraph and constructs the three-dimensional world with that information.

The BackgroundSound node is not a spatial sound rendering node. Its purpose is to facilitate the use of ‘ambient’ background sounds within the Java application. The audio input to this node is normally a mono or stereo audio file. A detailed description of the parameters for this node can be found in Appendix D.

1.1 The Sound Node

The Sound Node is the highest level on the sound rendering hierarchical tree. It contains parameters that are common to all sound nodes, a list of these parameters can be found in Table 1. A SceneGraph can contain an unlimited number of Sound Nodes – this is equivalent to an unlimited number of sound sources. This is clearly dependent upon both the system and hardware resources that are available to the rendering device. In order to guarantee that certain sounds are audible at any particular time a priority flag is set. Sound nodes of priority

¹ Version 1.2_alpha1, August 2, 1999

one have the highest priority and will be played at the expense of less ordered sounds. For example, in a multimedia conferencing application the participants' voices would have to have a higher priority over, say, background music.

When the user traverses an area in the SceneGraph that has a Sound Node, the sound is activated. The 'scheduling region' information delineates the area within which a sound will be activated. An example of this would be a computer game; when the user reaches a particular level or location within the game then an appropriate sound is played.

Source information parses meta-data from the sound file. This data contains information such as the author's name, copyright details, origin, sampling rate, number of channels, etc. There is also a parameter for looping the sound. This employs two loop points to define the beginning and end of the loop and also a loop counter that specifies the number of times the sound is to be repeated. Loop functionality does not apply to streamed sources.

Table 1

Sound Node Parameters

Location of the sound data
An amplitude scale factor
Priority flag
Source information
A bounding, or scheduling region
Sound looping functionality
Play duration
Flags denoting whether or not the sound should play, or play 'silently' to the end when the sound is disabled

(Note: Appendix A contains the details of the Sound Node including its Constants, Constructors, and Methods)

1.1.1 Spatial Rendering

The Sound Node itself does not address the spatial rendering of the sound source; this is accomplished in one of two ways. Firstly, by explicitly constructing the spatial attributes of the sound using either the PointSound Node or the ConeSound Node, or secondly, by configuring the acoustical characteristic of an environment using the Soundscape Node.

The first technique, constructing the spatial attributes, is dependent upon the type of sound source that is being used. If the sound source is a uniformly radiating sound (positional sound) then the PointSound node should be used, otherwise the developer should use the ConeSound node (directional sound).

Before examining both of these nodes we should first address the process of distance attenuation that is implemented in the Java 3D specification. According to Dale [3],

“Java 3D applies distance attenuation arrays to the amplitude of positional and directional sound sources, and applies angular attenuation arrays to amplitude of directional sound sources.”

When a sound object is created it has to be assigned an initialGain value; if this field is empty then the value defaults to 1.0 (where 1.0 is the maximum gain and 0.0 is the equivalent of a gain value of -60dB). In relation to the generic Sound Node no distance attenuation is

applied². This would seem to be a rather serious flaw in the specification as distance attenuation is one of the strongest cues in establishing depth perception for sound and should be accessible from the generic object [4]. If the developer did not want the sound to have distance attenuation then s/he could simply leave the distance field blank. One must also question whether a linear attenuation from 0dB to -60dB is a suitable model of natural process in distance based attenuation.

1.2 The PointSound Node

The PointSound node employs distance based attenuation of the gain as a means to convey depth or distance in a three-dimensional space; according to the Java 3D specification [5] the node,

“defines a spatially located sound whose waves radiate uniformly in all directions from some point in space”.

PointSound shares many of the attributes that are found in the generic Sound Node with two important additions: (1) distance based gain attenuation and (2) location in three dimensions. Depth, or distance, is achieved by attenuating the gain of the source based upon the source’s position in relation to the listener’s position.

Figure 2

These gain scale factors are set using the `setDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])` method. If this method is not set then no distance-based gain attenuation is performed – this is the same as setting the scale factor to 1.0. Having set the gain scale factor, an array of distance and gain values is constructed. When the program is running and the user’s position

² Having examined the specification thoroughly I have not found any mention of distance attenuation with respect to the generic Sound Node. I have contacted the author of the specification and I am awaiting clarification of this point.

changes the algorithm will determine the user's position and interpolate the gain scale factor from the values within the array. The interpolation is a linear process. Again, it is debatable whether linear attenuation is the best process to use for distance attenuation. One could argue that because there are no environmental parameters set the only option available is that of linear based attenuation.

An example of this can be seen in figure 2³. In this instance the distance-gain array has the following values (Table 2):

Table 2

Distance	Gain
10.0	1.0
12.0	0.9
16.0	0.5
17.0	0.3
20.0	0.16
24.0	0.12
28.0	0.05
30.0	0.0

This system is a rather simplified process and hence, there are certain built-in safeguards. If the distance between the listener and the source is less than the distance specified in the first field of the array it will be assigned the gain value of the first gain field. Also, if the distance is greater than the distance of the last field in the array it will be assigned the gain value of the last field of the array. For instance, assume that the listener is 15.0 units of distance⁴ from the source then the value of the gain scale factor is 0.4 – this value is arrived at by interpolating between the value of the gain fields before and proceeding it.

The PointSound Node also defines the source in terms of a three-dimensional coordinate system using the 'setPosition' method. The developer has the option to define the source position as a single point with an x, y, and z position of type floating point, or as three separate floating point fields, each corresponding to the x, y, and z positions. These points conform to azimuth, elevation and distance in a 3D aural space. Java 3D Cartesian coordinates are right-handed systems by default.

1.3 The ConeSound Node

The ConeSound Node is similar to the PointSound Node with a few additions. The PointSound Node is limited to simple distance attenuation whereas the ConeSound node

³ This diagram is quoted from the Java 3D specification, figure 5-2, page 80.

⁴ For this case, we assume the unit to be distance in meters.

facilitates separate forward and backward attenuation (allowing the developer to create an elliptically radiating source), angular attenuation, and filtering. The ConeSound node also introduces the direction vector. This vector defines the direction of the source's radiation. Specifying two distance gain attenuation arrays will generate an elliptically radiating pattern, or boundary, around the source, see Figure 3. These arrays behave as per the distance gain arrays of the PointSound node. The 'backDistance' attenuation array defines increasing distances along the negative direction vector. If only one distance attenuation array is declared then the distance attenuation is defined as a spherical distance attenuation system as can be seen in Figure 4 (the same as the PointSound node).

Figure 3 Elliptical Pattern

Figure 4 Spherical Pattern

The ConeSound node allows for angular attenuation of distance. This is calculated by determining the angle between the source-listener vector and the direction vector of the source. The 'setAngularAttenuation' method defines the angle in radians, the gain scale factor, and the filter setting. If no gain scale factor is given then the value defaults to 1.0, which is the equivalent of no gain change. This information is then put into a triple array, from which the value of the angular attenuation and filter setting are interpolated for the listener's position. If the angular distance is less than the value of the first field in the array then the values of the first field are applied. "This creates a conical region around the listener

within which the sound is uniformly attenuated by the first gain and the first filter of the array.”[6] As per the PointSound node, if the angular distance is greater than the last field of the array, then the last gain scale factor and filter setting are applied.

The filter setting is limited to a Low-Pass Filter, the developer specifies the cut-off frequency, or alternatively no value (implies no filtering). Since the specification only facilitates simple low-pass filtering, a situation that would involve multiple filters or cascading of filters, for instance a sound that is to be attenuated by angular and distance filters, would result in duplication of effort. The present filter option is not very sophisticated and it is intended that later versions of the Java 3D API specification will incorporate more refined filter options, such as full FIR filtering [7].

An example of a ConeSound Node can be found in Figure 5, the values of the array can be seen in Table 3:

Table 3

Angular Distance ⁵	Gain Scale Factor	Filter Settings
0.12	0.8	NO_FILTER
0.26	0.6	18000.0
0.32	0.4	15000.0
0.40	0.2	11000.0

Figure 5 ConeSound attenuation

1.4 Soundscape Node

This node configures the acoustical properties of the listener’s environment. An unlimited number of Soundscape nodes can be contained within a scene. The defined Soundscape node

⁵ The angular distance contains a set of increasing floating point numbers from 0 to π .

region determines which sets of acoustical properties are to be used and is distinct from the scheduling region mentioned earlier. As a result of being able to specify several Soundscape node regions one can generate a number of aural environments within the scene. For instance, within the one scene there could be three rooms, each with a different acoustical signature (figure 6). Alternatively, with more detailed scene description one could setup a number of acoustical regions within a single room using a number of Soundscape nodes.

To determine which Soundscape node is activated we rely upon the ViewPlatform Node. This node returns the viewer’s position and viewing direction or aural direction in this case, to the SceneGraph. Hence, it is the viewer’s position and not the position of the sound source that activates the relevant Soundscape node.

Figure 6 Three Soundscape Nodes in one SceneGraph

Region one reverberant	Region two dull
	Region three dry

1.5 AuralAttributes Object

The acoustical properties, i.e. reverberation and atmospheric attributes of the Soundscape node, are specified in the AuralAttributes Object. The AuralAttributes Object is a component object of the Soundscape Node. It specifies the following aural properties: reverberation, Doppler effect, distance frequency filtering, and atmospheric rolloff. Table 4 contains a list of the parameters and their default values for when an AuralAttribute Object is first constructed.

Table 4

Parameter	Default Value
attributeGain	1.0
rolloff	1.0
reflectionCoeff	0.0
reverbDelay	0.0
reverbBounds	null
reverbOrder	0
distanceFilter	null
frequencyScaleFactor	1.0
velocityScaleFactor	1.0

The AuralAttributes Object describes reverberation with three components; delay time, reflection coefficient, and feedback loop. Delay time is used to calculate the amount of time taken for the sound to reach the listener having undergone one reflection. This component is

either set explicitly or implied by the bounding regions of the volume. Note that the bounding region is not necessarily the same as the region specified for the Soundscape Node. Delay time is measured in milliseconds.

The reflection coefficient is used to determine the attenuation factor for the sound. The reflection coefficients represent the reflective or absorption properties of the environment. A value of 1.0 represents an un-attenuated sound and a value of 0.0 represents a sound that has been fully absorbed. These coefficients are applied as a uniform attenuation across the spectrum. This is not a very refined scheme as most reflective/absorptive materials alter the spectrum of the sound in a non-uniform manner. Using the present implementation of reflection/absorption there would be very little timbral difference between a sound that has been reflected by plaster and one that has been reflected by a metallic object.

The final component, feedback loop, specifies the number of times a sound is reflected or the order of reflection. If the feedback loop has a value of 0.0 no reverberation is performed, if it is set to one then the listener hears an echo, and if it is set to -1 the reverberation will continue until the amplitude of the signal dies to -60dB . This is known as *effective zero* in the Java 3D specification [8]. Effective zero relies upon a -6dB drop in gain for every doubling of distance (inverse square law). Values between 0.0 and 1.0 refer to the number of iterations of the loop. Figure 7⁶ illustrates the various parameters associated with the reverberation technique used in the specification.

Figure 7 Reverberation parameters

The parameter 'attributeGain' is used to alter the speed of sound in order to mimic the effects of atmospheric change. The default value is .344 meters per millisecond, this refers to the speed of sound at room temperature. This value is then altered by the gain scale value specified by the developer. A value greater than 1.0 will increase the speed of sound and conversely a value less than 1.0 will decrease the speed of sound.

The Doppler effect is achieved by taking the value of the speed of sound, multiplying it by the velocity scale factor (which is the change of speed relative to the listener's position) and

⁶ Taken from the Java 3D API specification, page 145.

then proportionally applying the frequency scale values. If the velocity scale factor is 0.0 no Doppler effect is processed.

2.0 Evaluation

So far, I have reviewed the spatial sound features available in the Java 3D specification with some commentary on areas of weak implementation. The following contains a critique of the spatial sound features with respect to the Dual Modes and the Auditory Framework.

2.1 Dual Modes

This current version of the specification employs both physical and perceptual models of spatial sound rendering. Both the PointSound and ConeSound Nodes are based upon the physical model exclusively, whilst the Soundscape Node is based upon the perceptual model. However, the implementation of these Nodes does not cover all of the possibilities within the two modes. For example, it is not possible to create a reverberant sound independent of the environment within which it placed. Hence, all of the perceptual properties within this specification are tied directly to the environment (Soundscape Node).

The use of the physical mode is rather limited as well. This is highlighted by the fact that one cannot assign reflective or absorptive properties (coefficients) to objects within an environment. In addition to this, the shape of the room cannot be specified (in terms of its acoustical properties); it is automatically assumed that all rooms are rectangular in the Java 3D specification. One could create a spherical room but the acoustical signature will depict the acoustic of a rectangular room.

It is also difficult to mix both the physical and perceptual models. For instance, if one designed a source using the ConeSound node that had a particular radiation pattern and gain property, those characteristics would not be taken into account if the sound were activated in a Soundscape environment. In essence most of the spatial information from the ConeSound node would be destroyed by the acoustical properties of the Soundscape node, leading to nonsensical spatial information.

2.2 Auditory Framework

Having evaluated some of the features of the specification with the Dual Modes it now remains to examine those features in more detail using the primitives of the Auditory Framework.

2.2.1 Source

As mentioned above one cannot assign sophisticated spatialisation parameters, such as reverberation, to a sound source. The PointSound Node enables the developer to generate a sound with a directionally radiating source, whilst the ConeSound offers two choices of radiating patterns: spherical as per the PointSound Node and elliptical. The elliptical shape facilitates two different attenuation vectors and incorporates angular attenuation and basic filtering. However, there is no means of generating a complex radiating pattern for a source within the present version of the specification.

2.2.2 Medium

There is primarily one parameter available for manipulating the medium. That is, the speed of sound parameter can be used to implement the Doppler effect. In addition to this, one would have expected to be able to specify a filtering process to mimic the absorptive effects of humidity, etc. and to be able to choose a different medium.

2.2.3 Environment

The environment can be configured using the Soundscape Node. The developer can specify the reverberation properties of a room. As mentioned previously, the manipulation of environment's acoustic properties is quite limited in this version of the specification. There is no facility for complex geometries, or for replicating complex interactions with the environment such as occlusion and diffraction.

2.2.4 Listener

The listener primitive is satisfied by the fact that all sound rendering is listener-oriented; this is apparent from the use of scheduling bounds and various activating regions. All aspects of sound rendering are undertaken from the listener's "viewing platform" or viewpoint. Hence, all of the spatial properties, from distance-attenuation to Doppler effect, are rendered relative to the listener's position.

Aspects such as visual-association are not possible in this version of the specification. For instance, a room's acoustic signature is generated irrespective of the number and type of objects within the environment. While this might be desirable in a perceptual context it sends conflicting cues to the viewer/listener from a physical mode perspective. An example of this would be a room that contains many objects with high absorption materials whilst the audible sound has the impression of a very reverberant environment.

3.0 Conclusion

It is apparent from the above that the implementation of sound spatialisation in version 1.2 of the Java 3D API specification, while commendable, is not very sophisticated. This is surprising when one considers that Java is very popular for multimedia development. Restricting the developer to one kind of filter and not implementing standard features, such as source-reverberation properties, does not facilitate the development of sophisticated spatialised sound environments. That said, Java is a relatively young language and is expected to mature more over the next few years. Already the programming language is at version 2 and it is expected that by the end of the year the 3D API specification will also move to version 2. One can only hope that more spatialisation features will be added to make the Java 3D API set a truly robust and comprehensive tool for spatially rendering sound in three-dimensional environments.

References

- [1] Spatial Sound Description in Virtual Environments, Murphy, D., The Proceedings of the Cambridge Music Processing Colloquium, September 1999.
- [2] Creating Interactive Virtual Acoustic Environments, Savioja, L., Huopaniemi, J., Lokki, T., and Väänänen, R., J. Audio Eng. Soc., vol. 47, No. 9, 1999
- [3] A Machine-Independent 3D Positional Sound Application Programmer Interface To Spatial Audio Engines, Dale, W., The Proceedings Of The AES 16th International Conference, April 1999, p160.
- [4] An Introduction To The Psychology Of Hearing, Moore, J., p213, Academic Press, London, 1997, p213.
- [5] Java 3D API Specification, version 1.2_alpha, Sun Microsystems, Inc., August 1999, p77
- [6] Ibid. p86
- [7] Ibid. p525
- [8] Ibid. p145

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Appendices

Appendix A Sound Node

Constants

Note: all of these constants are preceded by the declaration 'public static final int'.

Allow_Sound_Data_Read	Allow_Sound_Data_Write
Allow_Initial_Gain_Read	Allow_Initial_Gain_Write
Allow_Loop_Read	Allow_Loop_Write
Allow_Release_Read	Allow_Release_Write
Allow_Cont_Play_Read	Allow_Cont_Play_Write
Allow_Enable_Read	Allow_Enable_Write
Allow_Scheduling_Bounds_Read	Allow_Scheduling_Bounds_Write
Allow_Priority_Read	Allow_Priority_Write
Allow_Duration_Read	Allow_Duration_Write
Allow_Channels_Used_Read	
Allow_Is_Playing_Read	
Allow_Is_Ready_Read	

Constructors

Parameter	Default Value
soundData	null
initialGain	1.0
loop	0
release flag	false
continuous flag	false
on switch	false
scheduling region	null
priority	1.0

Methods

public final void setSoundData(MediaContainer soundData)	public final MediaContainer getSoundData()
public final void setInitialGain(float amplitude)	public final float getInitialGain()
public final void setLoop(int loopCount)	public final int getLoop()
public final void setReleaseEnable(boolean state)	public final boolean getReleaseEnable()
public final void setContinuousEnable(boolean state)	public final boolean getContinuousEnable()
public final setSchedulingBounds(Bounds region)	public final Bounds getSchedulingBounds()
public final void setSchedulingBoundingLeaf(BoundingLeaf region)	public final BoundingLeaf getSchedulingBoundingLeaf()
public final void setPriority(float ranking)	public final float getPriority()
public final void setEnable(boolean state)	public final boolean getEnable()

```
public final boolean isReady()
public final boolean isPlaying()
public final boolean isPlayingSilently()
public final long    getDuration()
public final int     getNumberOfChannelsUsed()
```

Appendix B PointSound Node

Constants

Note: all of these constants are preceded by the declaration 'public static final int'.

```
int ALLOW_POSITION_READ           int ALLOW_POSITION_READ
int ALLOW_DISTANCE_GAIN_READ      int ALLOW_DISTANCE_GAIN_WRITE
```

Constructors

```
Public PointSound(MediaContainer soundData, float initialGain, Point3f position)
Public PointSound(MediaContainer soundData, float initialGain, float posX, float posY, float posZ)
```

Methods

Note: all of these methods are preceded by the declaration 'public final'.

```
void setPosition(Point3f position)           void getPosition(Point3f position)
void setPosition(float x, float y, float z)
void setDistanceGain(Point2f attenuation[])  void getDistanceGain(Point2f attenuation[])
void setDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])  void getDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])
int getDistanceGainLength()
```

Appendix C ConeSound Node

Constants

Note: all of these constants are preceded by the declaration 'public static final int'.

```
int ALLOW_DIRECTION_READ           int ALLOW_DIRECTION_READ
int ALLOW_ANGULAR_ATTENUATION_READ int ALLOW_ANGULAR_ATTENUATION_WRITE
```

Constructors

```
public ConeSound(MediaContainer soundData, float initialGain, Point3f position, Vector3f direction)
public ConeSound(MediaContainer soundData, float initialGain, float posX, float posY, float posZ, float dirX, float dirY, float dirZ)
```

Methods

Note: all of these methods are preceded by the declaration 'public final'.

```
void setDistanceGain(Point2f frontAttenuation[],Point2f backAttenuation[])
void setDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])
Void setDistance(float frontDistance[], float frontGain[], float backDistance[], float backGain[])
Void setBackDistanceGain(Point2f attenuation[])
Void setBackDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])

void setDirection(Vector3f direction)
void setDirection(float x, float y, float z)
void setAngularAttenuation(Point2f attenuation[])
void setAngularAttenuation(Point3f attenuation[])
void setAngularAttenuation(float angle[], float angularGain[], float frequencyCutoff[])

void getDistanceGain(Point2f frontAttenuation[],Point2f backAttenuation[])
void getDistanceGain(float distance[], float gain[])
Void getDistance(float frontDistance[], float frontGain[], float backDistance[], float backGain[])

void getDistanceGain(Point2f frontAttenuation[], Point2f backAttenuation[])
void getDirection(Vector3f direction)

void getAngularAttenuation(Point3f attenuation[])
void getAngularAttenuation(float angle[], float angularGain[], float frequencyCutoff[])
int getAngularAttenuationLength()
```

Appendix D Soundscape Node

Constants

Note: all of these constants are preceded by the declaration 'public static final int'.

```
int ALLOW_APPLICATION_BOUNDS_READ      int ALLOW_APPLICATION_BOUNDS_READ
int ALLOW_ATTRIBUTES_READ              int ALLOW_ATTRIBUTES_WRITE
```

Constructors

```
public Soundscape(Bounds region, AuralAttributes attributes)
```

Methods

Note: all of these methods are preceded by the declaration 'public final'.

```
Void setApplicationBounds(Bounds region)      Bounds setApplicationBounds()
Void setApplicationBoundingLeaf(BoundingLeaf region)      BoundingLeaf getApplicationBoundingLeaf()
Void setAuralAttributes(AuralAttributes attributes)      AuralAttributes getAuralAttributes()
```

Appendix E BackgroundSound Node

Constants

None

Constructors

```
public BackgroundSound(MediaContainer soundData, float initialGain, int loopCount, boolean release, boolean continuous, boolean enable, Bounds region, float priority)
```

Methods

None

Appendix F AuralAttributes Object

Constants

Note: all of these constants are preceded by the declaration 'public static final int'.

ALLOW_ATTRIBUTE_GAIN_READ	ALLOW_ATTRIBUTE_GAIN_WRITE
ALLOW_ROLLOFF_READ	ALLOW_ROLLOFF_WRITE
ALLOW_REFLECTION_COEFFICIENT_READ	ALLOW_REFLECTION_COEFFICIENT_WRITE
ALLOW_REVERB_DELAY_READ	ALLOW_REVERB_DELAY_WRITE
ALLOW_REVERB_ORDER_READ	ALLOW_REVERB_ORDER_WRITE
ALLOW_DISTANCE_FILTER_READ	ALLOW_DISTANCE_FILTER_WRITE
ALLOW_FREQUENCY_SCALE_FACTOR_READ	ALLOW_FREQUENCY_SCALE_FACTOR_WRITE
ALLOW_VELOCITY_SCALE_FACTOR_READ	ALLOW_VELOCITY_SCALE_FACTOR_WRITE

Constructors

Parameter	Default Value
attributeGain	1.0
rolloff	1.0
reflectionCoeff	0.0
reverbDelay	0.0
reverbBounds	null
reverbOrder	0
distanceFilter	null
frequencyScaleFactor	1.0
velocityScaleFactor	1.0

Methods

Note: all of these methods are preceded by the declaration 'public final'.

void setAttributesGain(float gain)	float getAttributeGain()
void setRolloff(float rolloff)	float getRoll()
void setReflectionCoefficient(float coefficient)	float getReflectionCoefficient()
void setReverbDelay(float reverbDelay)	float getReverbDelay()
void setReverbBounds(Bounds reverbVolume)	Bounds getReverbBounds()
void setReverbOrder(int reverbOrder)	int getReverbOrder()
void setDistanceFilter(Point2f attenuation[])	void getDistanceFilter(Point2f attenuation[])
void setDistanceFilter(float distance[], float frequencyCutoff[])	void getDistanceFilter(float distance[], float frequencyCutoff[])
	int getDistanceFilterLength()
void setFrequencyScaleFactor(float frequencyScaleFactor)	float getFrequencyScaleFactor()
void setVelocityScaleFactor(float velocityScaleFactor)	float getVelocityScaleFactor()